

Human-centred artificial intelligence-based solutions for smart manufacturing

The consortium of **AI-PRISM** (AI-Powered human-centred Robot Interactions for Smart Manufacturing) is pleased to announce the launch of this joint initiative, granted by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme.

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with **human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable and high-quality European manufacturing industry.**

To do so, we will develop an integrated and scalable environment with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

The AI-PRISM project focuses on improving manufacturing processes through AI-based solutions that increase manufacturers' productivity and customer satisfaction.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars.

1. **A human-centred collaborative robotic platform** oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. **A human-robot cooperative environment** powered by trustworthy AI.
3. **Social human-agent-robots teams collaboration** — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. **An open-access network portal** to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability and large-scale deployment, we will carry out demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in **four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors** — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances and electronics —, **types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility.**

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, **AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes**, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the next three years, **25 partners from 12 countries** will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

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